

EFFECTS OF FREEZE-THAW CYCLES ON FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED CFRP JOINTS

Poster Number: 1302

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1. Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) tanks bring many advantages for liquid hydrogen storage.

Hydrogen-powered aircraft

Advantages of using CFRP cryogenic tank

- Lightweight compared to metals
- Passive utilization of anisotropy in design
- Low thermal conductivity to prevent boil-off

Understanding of properties in adhesive parts (e.g., cylinder/boss part) is important considering various factors including environmental effects.

Refueling: Freezing ↔ Maintenance: Thawing

- Effects of **freeze-thaw (FT) cycles** must be taken into consideration.
- Repeated FT cycles may trigger damage of adhesive resin due to volumetric expansion of water molecules²⁾.
- Correlation between fracture mechanisms and mechanical properties of adhesive joints are not fully understood.

Objectives

Elucidating the effects of FT cycles on fracture toughness of adhesively bonded CFRP joints

- **Mode I fracture toughness tests** on moisture-absorbing adhesively bonded CFRP joints after FT cycles
- **Tensile tests of bulk adhesive** for correlating the property changes of adhesively bonded CFRP joints
- **Fracture surface observations** of DCB specimens

1) <https://www.airbus.com/en/innovation/zero-emission/hydrogen/zeroe>, 2) S.K. Mital, et al., NASA/TM, 2006-214346 (2006).

2. Experimental procedure

Test materials and specimens

Specimens for weight change

- Materials: AF163-2M (12.5 × 12.5 × t1.2 mm)

Tensile test specimens of bulk adhesive

- Materials: AF163-2M (90 × 10 × t1.2 mm)

Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens

- Adhesive: Structural epoxy adhesive film (AF163-2M, 3M Company)
- Adherends: Unidirectional CFRP (T700S/2592, Toray Industries, Inc.)
- Stacking sequence of the laminates: [0]₃₀
- Surface treatment: Sanding
- Initial delamination: 13 μm thick polymer film

Procedure for moisture absorption (MA)

- Maintained for 30 days (720 h) at 60 °C and 95% RH in environmental chamber

Freeze-thaw (FT) cycles

- Exposed to 75 FT cycles using environmental chamber
- FT cycles consisting of freezing at -50 °C and thawing at 25 °C

Name of specimens	MA (720 h)	75 FT cycles
Control		
MA	✓	
MA + FT	✓	✓

Test environment

- Two temperatures were chosen to consider operating environment (room temperature (RT), -50 °C).

DCB specimen

DCB test @ RT

DCB test @ -50 °C

3. Results and discussion

Weight change of bulk adhesive

$$W = \frac{m_1 - m_0}{m_0} \times 100$$

W : Weight change (water absorption)
 m_0 : Mass before water absorption
 m_1 : Mass after water absorption

➤ Water possibly evaporated during the FT cycles.

Tensile tests of bulk adhesive

- Ultimate stress decreased due to moisture absorption.
- **The effect of plasticization by water molecules was observed³⁾.**
- FT cycles on MA resulted in a slight increase in ultimate stress.
- **Evaporation of water during FT cycles was possibly caused.**
- Ultimate stress increased but maximum strain at failure decreased significantly from RT to -50 °C.
- **Changes in bulk adhesive properties at low temperature were observed.**

Combined effects of MA and FT cycles on mechanical properties of bulk adhesive

3) K. Kishimoto, et al., ASME, Applied Mechanics Division 187, pp.11-16 (1994).

Mode I fracture toughness

- Fracture toughness decreased due to moisture absorption.
- **Fracture toughness of MA specimens reflected bulk adhesive properties (decrease in ultimate stress).**
- Further decrease in fracture toughness occurred due to FT cycles although increase in ultimate stress and maximum strain at failure were observed in bulk adhesive.
- **Unlike bulk adhesive, the effects may be irreversible in adhesively bonded joints.**
- Fracture toughness decreased at -50 °C.
- **Decrease in the maximum strain of bulk adhesive at -50 °C was well reflected.**

Fracture surface observations of DCB specimens

- Change in fracture surface was not observed at micro scale owing to FT cycles.
- **The effects of FT cycles were due to changes in properties at molecular scale.**

4. Conclusions

Mode I fracture toughness tests were conducted to investigate the effect of FT cycles on the mechanical properties of MA adhesively bonded CFRP joints. In addition, the results were correlated with bulk adhesive properties and fracture surface observations. The findings can be summarized as follows.

- Fracture toughness decreased owing to moisture absorption, and further decreased after FT cycles.
- Fracture toughness decreased for all conditions at -50 °C compared to RT results.
- Fracture surfaces remained unchanged after MA and FT cycles.

This work was partly supported by a grant-in-aid for research from the Faculty of Systems Design, Tokyo Metropolitan University.